

QURILISH KONSTRUKSIYALARI VA XAVFSIZLIGI

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Kirish. Kapital qurilish Respublikamiz xalq xo'jaligida muhim ahamiyatga ega. Har qanday davlatning material-texnik bazasini yaratish kapital qurilishsiz tassavur qilib bo'lmaydi.

Qurilish konstruksiyalari - har qanday bino va sun'iy inshootlarni qurish, turarjoy binolari, jamoat, sanoat va qishloq xo'jalik binolari, ko'priklar, katta hajmli imoratlar, quvurlar va inshootlarning asosi hisoblanadi. Bino va inshootni qurish uchun sarflangan xarajatlarning asosiy qismi konstruksiyalarga to'g'ri keladi.

Hozirgi kunda amalga oshirilayotgan katta hajmdagi kapital qurilishlar, qurilish konstruksiyalaridan samarali foydalanish rivojining juda tez jadallashuviga turtki bo'ldi - konstruksiyalarning turlari va ulardan tayyorlanadigan xomashyolar to'xtovsiz takomillashib bormoqda. Shu boisdan ularni hisoblash, loyihalash va tiklash usullari ham takomillashtirilmoqda.

Qurilish konstruksiyalarini hisoblashdan maqsad qurilishning samaradorligini oshirish, uning konstruktiv sxemalarini ixchamlashtirish va konstruksiyalarni tiplashtirish asosida, iloji boricha ko'proq tayyorligini oshirish bo'lsa, ikkinchisi - bu imoratlarni raqobatbardosh, yuqori sifatli, shinam va vazifaviy qulay bo'lishini ta'minlashdir. Shu tufayli mexanizatsiyalashtirilgan va avtomatlashtirilgan texnologik arayonlarni qo'llash bilan bir qatorda qurilish maydonchalarida bajariladigan ishlarga keng imkoniyatlar ochib berildi. Qurilish konstruksiyalari ularda qo'llanadigan materiallariga ko'ra metalli (odatda po'latdan), g'isht-toshli, betonli va temirbetonli, yog'och yoki plastmassali konstruksiyalarga bo'linadi.

XVI-XVII asrlarda bino va inshootlarni qurishda dastlab bog'lovchi unsur sifatida foydalanildi, keyinchalik XVIII asrdan boshlab metallni qurilish konstruksiyasi sifatida qo'llaniladi. Birinchi cho'yan ko'priki XVIII asrda (Angliyada 1779 yili va 1784 yili Rossiyada) quriladi.

XIX asrda muayyan shakldagi metall buyumlarning ishlab chiqarilishi qurilishda ishlatiladigan unsurlarini oqilona kesimlarini hosil qilinishiga sabab bo'ldi. Po'lat konstruksiyalarining unsurlarini yig'ishda payvandlashni qo'llanilishi konstruksiyalarni ishlab chiqarishda mehnat sarfini ancha kamayishiga va qurilishda keng miqyosda qo'llanilishiga olib keldi.

XIX asrning o'rtalarida yangi material - temirbeton paydo bo'ldi, unda beton va metallning maqbul mutanosiblikda ishlatiladi. O'sha davrda konstruksiyalarni hisobi paydo bo'ldi va rivojlantirildi. Konstruksiyalarni hisoblashning ilmiy usullari doimo rivojlantirilib kelinmoqda.

Vazirlar Mahkamasining 2018-yil 31-iyul, 603-son qarori bilan tasdiqlangan "O'zbekiston Respublikasi Qurilish vazirligi to'g'risida"gi NIZOM da qurilish vazirligi o'z vakolati doirasida quyidagilarni amalga oshiradi:

-binolar, inshootlar va ularning alohida yelementlariga bo'lgan xavfsizlik talablarini, shuningdek, bino va inshootlarning yenergiya samaradorligini oshirish bo'yicha chora-tadbirlarni ishlab chiqadi;

-shaharsozlik faoliyatida mahsulotlar, ishlar va xizmatlar xavfsizligiga qo'yiladigan majburiy talablarga taalluqli texnik jihatdan tartibga solish sohasida ishlar bajarilishini ta'minlaydi;

-arxitektura, loyihalash va qurilish sohasida malakali kadrlarni tayyorlashga tizimli asosda ko'maklashishni ta'minlaydi.

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining "O'zbekiston Respublikasi qurilish sohasini modernizatsiyalash, jadal va innovasion rivojlantirishning 2020—2025-yillarga mo'ljallangan strategiyasi to'g'risida"gi farmoyish loyihasida ko'rsatilganidek, O'zbekistonda qurilish sohasini modernizatsiyalash, jadal va innovasion rivojlantirishning asosiy yo'nalishlari sifatida quyidagilar belgilangan:

-o'qitishning zamonaviy va innovasion usullari qo'llanishini hisobga olgan holda qurilish yo'nalishidagi kadrlarni tayyorlash, qayta tayyorlash va malakasini oshirishni tashkil qilish tizimini takomillashtirish;

- qurilish obektlarida qurilish-montaj ishlarini bajarishda mehnat muhofazasi va xavfsizlik texnikasiga bo'lgan talablarni kuchaytirish kabi dolzarb masalalar qo'yilgan.

"Loyiha-qidiruv hamda qurilish-pudrat tashkilotlarining faoliyati samaradorligini oshirish, ular o'rtasida sog'lom raqobat muhitini shakllantirish maqsadida reyting tizimi yo'lga qo'yilayapti. Bu bilan loyihalovchi va quruvchining ishi bino foydalanishga topshirilib, barcha yutuq hamda kamchiliklarlar yuzaga chiqqach yemas, balki qurilish-montaj jarayonida baholab boriladi. Bu to'g'risida 2020 yil 9 noyabrda Vazirlar Mahkamasining 699-sonli "Loyiha-qidiruv va qurilish-pudrat tashkilotlari reytingini hisoblash va yuritish tartibini joriy yetish chora tadbirlari to'g'risida" gi qarori qabul qilindi. Ushbu me'yoriy hujjat asosida Loyiha-qidiruv va qurilish-pudrat tashkilotlari reytingini hisoblash va yuritish tartibi to'g'risida nizom ham tasdiqlandi."

Yendi qurilishlarning yelectron bazasi tuzilib tashkilotlarning reytingi ochiq va oshkoro tarzda baholanib boriladi.

Ushbu ma'ruza matnlari Respublikamizda qurilish sohasidagi islohotlarni amalga oshirish uchun "Bino, inshootlarni qurish va ishlash xavfsizligi" fanidan 5860100-"Hayotiy faoliyat xavfsizligi" ta'lim yo'nalishi bo'yicha malakali bakalavrlar tayyorlash uchun mo'ljallangan muhim manba bo'lib xizmat qiladi.

Qurilish-montaj ishlarini xavfsiz olib borish uchun montaj ishlari mutaxassislari bino va inshootlarni asosiy hajmiy-rejaviy va konstruksiyaviy yechimlarini, ularda qo'llaniladigan metall va temirbeton materiallarining fizik va mexanik xususiyatlarini bilishi, konstruksiyalarning unsurlarini hisobiy sxemalarini va ularning zo'riqish holatini montaj jarayonida va ulardan foydalanish davrida aniq tassovur eta bilishlari hamda, uncha murakkab bo'lmagan konstruksiyalarning unsurlarni hisoblay olishlari kerak.

Oxirgi o'n yilliklarda sanoatning taraqqiy etishi davomida Respublikamizda qurilish konstruksiyalari miqyosida texnikaviy o'sish kuzatildi. Sanoat bazasining kundan-kunga rivojlanishi, materiallar va ashyolarning mustahkamlik xususiyati ortmoqda, yangi zamonaviy kurinishdagi konstruksiyalar chiqarilmoqda (sendvich panellar, KNAUF materiallari, turli xil suvoq qorishmalar va qoplamalar va h.k.), ularning zavod sharoitda tayyorlanishi oshmoqda.

Temirbeton va fazoviy-strukturaviy konstruksiyalar keng miqyosda qo'llanilmoqda.

Fanning maqsadi qurilish konstruksiyalarini hisoblash va konstruksiyalash bo'yicha malaka hosil qilish, meyyoriy hujjatlardan va boshqa texnik adabiyotlardan foydalanish. Bino va inshootlar loyihalanishida har xil konstruksiyalarni qollash va konstrktiv echimlarni, konstruksiyalar tizimi asoslari bilan qurollantirish, konstruksiyalarni qo'llashda mantiqiy fikrlash, tasavur etish qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirish, bino va inshootlarni avariya holatlarni oldindan belgilash va ularni bartaraf qilish chora-tadbirlariga tayyorgarlik ishlarini bajarish mahoratiga ega bo'lish.

Xulosa. Fanning vazifasi Respublikamizda va xorijda bunyod etilayotgan, yangi qurilish yo'nalishlari bilan tanishtirish, qurilish materiallari hozirgi zamon talablariga javob berishi uchun davlatimizda standartlash, sertifikatlash va metrologiya asoslari, ishlabchiqarish sohasidagi fan va texnika yutuqlari, bino, inshootlarni xavfsiz ekspluatasiya sharoitlarini ta'minlash haqida tasavurga ega bo'lishi, binolarni qurish va barpo etishda loyihasidan foydalana olishi, arxitektura-qurilish jarayonida atrof-muhitni muhofazalash ko'nikma va malakalarini hosil qilishdir.

Metall konstruksiyalari materialning yuqori darajada mustahkamligi evaziga kam xussiy massasiga ega. Ularni maxsus zavodlarda tayyorlanishi va qurilish maydonida montaj qilinishi

uncha katta mehnat xarajatlarini talab qilmaydi. Ammo ularning zanglashga moyilligi foydalanish davrida esa, davriy ravishda bo'yash ishlariga ko'p xarajatlarni talab etadi.

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